

EARLY DIAGNOSIS AND TREATMENT OF ACUTE KIDNEY INJURY IN YOUNG CHILDREN UNDERGOING CARDIAC SURGERY

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Abstract. *Acute kidney injury (AKI), occurring during surgical correction of congenital heart defects (CHD), is one of the main causes of disability and mortality in young children worldwide, including in Uzbekistan. Perioperative mortality rates with renal complications in these interventions range from 20 to 100%. Acute kidney injury associated with cardiac surgery is a common and serious complication that dramatically worsens the prognosis and outcomes of surgeries. The article presents the results of perioperative treatment of AKI in children after cardiac surgery based on early diagnosis of renal dysfunction. New formulas for calculating SCF using Cystatin C allow more accurate assessment of renal function. Based on the proposed treatment regimens, positive clinical dynamics were observed in both groups, but the results in the second group were significantly pronounced. It is shown that early perioperative use of renal injury markers in combined nephro- cardiotropic therapy in young children affects the effectiveness of treatment, improving the outcomes of complex surgeries.*

Keywords: *acute kidney injury, congenital heart disease, risk factor, heart failure, milrinone, glomerular filtration rate, cystatin C, creatine, peritoneal dialysis.*

It is important to suggest that acute kidney injury (AKI) is a pressing issue in congenital heart disease (CHD) surgery and is considered one of the most common complications among hospital nosology [4]. The prevalence of perioperative AKI varies on average from 5 to 40%, while the incidence of early hospital mortality in the population of such patients increases significantly compared to children without cardiac surgery-associated renal injury [7, 12]. The increased risk of AKI is associated with the fact that cardiac surgery under artificial circulation (AC) and aortic occlusion (AO) leads to impaired blood flow and renal ischemia, systemic inflammation and oxidative stress [6].

Besides, additional predisposing factors include anatomical and functional immaturity of kidney nephrons in newborns and infants, low glomerular filtration rate, reduced cardiac output, arterial hypotension, and the need to use higher doses of inotropic drugs [6].

It is known to everyone that modern assessment of the severity and diagnosis of AKI is traditionally carried out in accordance with the KDIGO (Kidney Disease: Improving Global Outcomes) criteria, according to the RIFLE (2004) and AKIN (2007) classifications [3]. The proposed KDIGO criteria are widely used by doctors of various specialties: resuscitators, nephrologists, cardiovascular surgeons, and others.

It is not a secret to anyone that surgical outcomes have improved due to the improvement of surgical techniques and an increase in the number of operations, anesthetic and intensive care

protocols have significantly improved, as well as the principles of early diagnosis of perioperative complications, especially in young children. Today, cardiac anesthesiologists and resuscitators are interested in a personalized approach to the comprehensive treatment of renal dysfunction in the perioperative period and the development of strategic management protocols based on the stages of the disease, the degree of damage according to ultrasound diagnostics and the so-called renal markers.

In clinical practice, serum creatinine (Scr) and the glomerular filtration rate (eGFR) or creatinine clearance (Cr) calculated on its basis are most widely used to assess renal function in AKI. Since eGFR is the most reliable indicator reflecting renal function, the search for an accurate, low-trauma, simple and fast method for determining eGFR in pediatric practice is especially relevant [4].

Till today several dozen different methods for measuring eGFR have been proposed, but due to their complexity and high cost, the vast majority of them have not entered widespread practice. The study of the accuracy and reliability of new markers in assessing the degree of kidney damage and the possibility of their application in practice has become relevant. In modern literature, the issue of the validity of considering cystatin C (CysC) as the earliest marker of renal dysfunction in young children and as an acceptable informative formula for calculating SCF continues to be discussed [2, 8].

CysC is the most reliable indicator of renal function preservation, being a more sensitive indicator of SCF decrease than creatinine, which allows it to be considered an effective diagnostic criterion for acute kidney injury even with normal creatinine levels [1]. In 2012, experts from the Chronic Kidney Disease Epidemiology Collaboration (CKD-EPI) proposed formulas for calculating eGFR using CysC and a combination of sCr and CysC [6]. In our study, SCF in children was determined using a formula based on the concentration of creatinine and CysC (eGFR_{cys}) in the blood serum [11]. Perioperative measurement of eGFR_{cys} was an important part of the clinical assessment of renal function in children and allowed for timely and accurate diagnosis of AKI, as well as choosing the correct treatment tactics, including stabilization of the underlying disease and elimination of factors that have a negative impact on renal function. It should be noted that the complex of therapeutic and preventive measures for drug treatment usually includes drugs with nephroprotective and cardioprotective effects. Treatment should be aimed at maintaining cardiac output with normalization of arterial pressure (AP), improving renal perfusion, reducing proteinuria, eliminating anemia and hyperuricemia, removing excess fluid, maintaining acid-base balance in the blood, and normalizing electrolytes [5].

There is no doubt that the development and implementation of principles for early diagnostics of AKI after correction of complex CHD in children requires an integrated approach and solving a number of problems new to anesthesiology and resuscitation. First of all, the complex hemodynamic situation characteristic of CHD places special demands on general anesthesia and intensive care [7].

By this it can be determined the purpose of this study: to identify all potential factors for the development of renal dysfunction in young children with CHD, who underwent cardiac surgery and to confirm the significance of the dynamic assessment of eGFR_{cis} in predicting perioperative AKI and, consequently, to optimize the strategy for the comprehensive treatment of this complication.

Material and methods. The mentioned studies were conducted at “Cardiac Anesthesiology and Cardiac Resuscitation” Department from January 1, 2017 to March 31, 2023, on the basis of the Department of Surgery for Congenital Heart Diseases No. 1 and the Clinical Diagnostic Laboratory of the State Institution " Republican Scientific and Practical Medical Center of Surgery named after Academician V. Vakhidov ". The study included 105 children aged from 8 days to 32 months (Me – 17 months) with various types of CHD, operated on under CPB and OA. The following clinical parameters were prospectively assessed: age, body weight, patient category according to RACHS-1, duration of anesthesia and surgery, time of CPB and OA, duration of inotropic therapy, hypothermia, intraoperative blood loss.

Hourly diuresis, increase in urea and creatinine, calculation of eSCFcys, blood biochemistry, presence of high doses of diuretics, microalbuminuria were used for the diagnosis of AKI in the early postoperative period, as well as echocardiographic data (GE Logic 9, USA) for perioperative assessment of internal cardiac hemodynamics. All surgeries were performed under CPB (Advanced Perfusion System 1, Terumo, Japan) and cold cardioplegia (CP). Statistical processing of the obtained results was performed using the IBM SPSS Statistics program. Nonparametric criteria were used. The values were presented as median (Me) ± standard deviation (SD). Comparative analysis was performed using the χ^2 criterion and the Mann-Whitney criterion for mean values. The search for clinical risk factors was carried out by determining the risk of developing AKI, determining the p-value.

The inclusion criteria in this study were: a) age from birth to 36 months; b) the presence of various types of congenital heart disease; c) performing surgical intervention under conditions of cardiopulmonary bypass and cerebrovascular accident.

During the study, a methodological approach was used, which included: elimination of factors that have a negative impact on organ dysfunction, therapy of decompensated conditions, correction of metabolic acidosis, achievement of normovolemia, ensuring hemodynamic stability and respiratory support, reducing myocardial oxygen demand and improving the function of target organs.

Besides that, inotropic drugs were used to treat acute heart failure, which led to an increase in cardiac output (CO), the left ventricular stroke index (LVSI) and right ventricular stroke index (RVSI), a decrease in total pulmonary resistance (PR) and a decrease in total peripheral vascular resistance (TPVR). Inotropic agents such as adrenaline, dobutamine, milrinone improve myocardial contractility, and peritoneal dialysis (PD) was used if it was necessary with oligoanuria and severe congestion. Discussion of the study results: in young children, eGFRcys was calculated using the CKD-EPI Creatinine-Cystatin C formula (Chronic Kidney Disease Epidemiology Collaboration, 2021, [6]) based on sCr and CysC, and according to the results obtained, the patients were divided into 2 groups. The first group consisted of 71 (66.5%) patients with SCF \geq 90 ml/min/1.73 m², the second group - 34 (33.5%) patients with SCF < 89 ml/min/1.73 m². Comparative characteristics and the impact of perioperative risk factors on eGFR values in both groups are presented in Table 1.

According to the analysis of the obtained data, the differences between the groups for each of these indicators are statistically significant. Younger age, low body weight, distribution between RACHS-1 categories, duration of anesthesia and surgery, time of CPB and OA, hypothermia, inotropic therapy, intraoperative blood loss in the group of children with low SCF significantly differed compared to the group of children without renal dysfunction.

Table 1

The influence of perioperative risk factors on the values of eGFR in the study groups

Parametrs	Group 1	Group 2	P
	<i>SCF 90-140 ml/min/1.73 m² (n= 71)</i>	<i>SCF < 89 ml/min/1.73 m² (n= 34)</i>	
Age < 1 year.	29 (40.8 %)	18 (52.9 %)	$\chi^2 = 18.31$ p<0.05
Weigh < 5 kg	4.5±0.8	4.1±0.6	p<0.04
SCF 90-140 ml/min/	13 (18.3 %)	26 (76.4 %)	$\chi^2 = 26.45$ p<0.001
Anesthesia > 240 min	42 (59.1 %)	28 (82.3 %)	$\chi^2 = 22.18$ p<0.004
Surgery > 180 min	39 (54.9%)	30 (88.2 %)	$\chi^2 = 26.12$ p<0.002
IR > 60 min	41 (57.7 %)	27 (79.4 %)	$\chi^2 = 28.17$ p<0.001
OA > 30 min	38 (53.5%)	29 (82.3 %)	$\chi^2 = 28.39$ p<0.001
Hypothermia < 35 °C	36 (50.7 %)	31 (91.2 %)	$\chi^2 = 16.20$ p<0.05
Inotropes > 3 days	49 (69 %)	34 (100%)	$\chi^2 = 16.20$ p<0.05
Intraoperative blood loss, ml	190.8±20.5	230.7±35.4	$\chi^2 = 16.20$ p<0.05

Note: RASCH-1 - Risk adjustment for congenital heart surgery, CPB - artificial circulation, OA - aortic occlusion

Table 2

Comparative characteristics of perioperative indicators in the study groups

Indicators	<i>GFR indicators 90-140 ml/min/1 (group 1)</i>	<i>GFR <89 ml/min/1.73 m² (group 2) p</i>	p
Creatinine (mol/l)	25.3 ± 2.7	29.8 ± 2.1	p=0.04
Cystatin C (mg/l)	2.34 ± 0.9	5.2 ± 1.6	p<0.001
Decreased diuresis, ml/hour	1.2 ± 0.06	0.4 ± 0.08	p<0.001
microalbuminuria (µg/l)	78.8 ± 16.9	165.8 ± 14.3	p<0.001
GFR based on creatinine, ml/min/1.73 m²	109.3±6.8	84.1 ± 5.2	p<0.001

GFR based on cystatin C, ml/min/1.73 m²	91.8±1.7	67.2 ±1,5	p<0.001
Peritoneal dialysis, %	23%	54%	p<0.001

Note: GFR – glomerular filtration rate

Definitely, a significant decrease in hourly diuresis was noted in the 2nd group with a high increase in microalbuminuria ($p < 0.001$). Moreover, these changes also affected the values of eGFRcr/cisC due to severe renal dysfunction, which, in turn, are due to perioperative multiple factors ($p < 0.001$).

One of the main goals of using the calculated eGFRcis C indicators in the immediate postoperative period is to decide on the early installation of PD to prevent severe AKI in young children. According to the data presented in this table, the percentage of patients with PD in group 2 was significantly higher ($p < 0.001$). Due to the therapeutic effect of PD, it was possible to detoxify and remove excess fluid by stimulating the peritoneum.

Thus, determining the exact values of eGFRcis C has diagnostic value as a new predictor of kidney damage and predetermines therapeutic tactics and prognosis of the disease. SCF in young children, calculated using a specific formula according to Schwartz G.J. (2009), is most informative when using the serum concentration of cisC and, therefore, predetermines early implementation of PD to correct renal dysfunction.

With reduced values of eGFR (≤ 89 ml/min/1.73 m²) in order to study the effectiveness of cardiotropic therapy in the treatment of AKI associated with cardiac surgery (Table 3), in group 1a in children, a combination of inotropic drugs in the form of adrenaline, dobutamine and milrinone was used, and in group 2a, PD was added to this combination.

Table 3

The impact of treatment protocols in children with reduced eGFR in study groups

Indicators	eGFR ≤ 89 ml/min/1.73 m² (n= 34)			
	<i>Epinephrine±dobutamine+milrinone (n=21)</i>		<i>Epinephrine±dobutamine+milrinone and peritoneal dialysis (n=13)</i>	
	<i>Group 1a: before treatment</i>	<i>Group 1a: after treatment</i>	<i>Group 2a: before treatment</i>	<i>Group 2a: after treatment</i>
<i>Microalbuminuria (mg/L)</i>	178.8 ± 16.9	101.5 ± 14.3 ** (43.3%)	193.2 ± 24.1	65.7 ± 18.4 *** (66%)
<i>Creatinine (μmol/L)</i>	35.1 ± 1.87	32.8 ± 2.09 * (6.5 %)	36.7 ± 1.52	26.5 ± 1.49 (27.8 %) **
<i>Cystatin C, (mg/l)</i>	3.79± 0.14	2.15±1.47 * (43.3%)	3.86 ±0.12	1.16±0.09 *** (69.9%)
<i>GFR, ml/min/1</i>	73.4±5.2	93.2 ± 4.6 **	71.6 ± 2.5 *	107.4 ±1.9 ***
<i>Hyperlactatemia, > 3.0 mmol/l</i>	3.8± 0.21	2.4±0.13 * (36.8%)	3.95 ±0.27	2.1±0.18 *** (46.8%)

*Note: SCF - glomerular filtration rate. * - reliability of the difference in indicators before and after treatment: * -p<0.05., ** -p<0.01., *** -p<0.001.*

Against the background of low eGFR and the therapy received in the intensive care unit, positive dynamics were observed in patients of group 2a compared to group 1a, and a clear decrease in the concentration of microalbuminuria was noted: 101.5 ± 14.3 mg / l versus 65.7 ± 18.4 mg / l ($p < 0.001$), creatinine - 32.8 ± 2.09 μ mol / l versus 26.5 ± 1.49 μ mol / l ($p < 0.05$) and CysC - 2.15 ± 1.47 mg / l versus 1.16 ± 0.09 mg / l ($p < 0.05$).

Moreover, the dynamics of changes in eGFR in both subgroups showed that the values were better in children using PD during the entire observation period, starting from the moment of its installation after the end of the operation ($p < 0.001$). When comparing both subgroups by serum lactate levels, it was noted that during the first postoperative days, high hyperlactatemia levels persisted, which characterized severe heart failure, decreased cardiac output, tissue hypoxia, and impaired microcirculation, which entailed decompensated metabolic acidosis ($p < 0.05$). Against the background of the main treatment with cardiotropic drugs, the concentration of lactate in the blood of children in group 1a was at the level of 3.6 ± 0.21 mmol/l and 3.95 ± 0.27 mmol/l in group 2a, with no intergroup difference ($p > 0.05$). In both subgroups of the study, dynamic changes in lactate concentration were observed on the 2nd day after the end of the operation ($p < 0.05$), a decrease in the level of lactatemia began only 48 hours after the operation and significantly continued until the end of the 3rd postoperative day to 2.4 ± 0.13 mmol / l ($p < 0.001$) in group 1a and to 2.1 ± 0.18 mmol / l in group 2a ($p < 0.001$).

Thus, according to the results of the presented table, in both subgroups, all indicators of renal function were associated with the development of AKI. After the proposed therapy, it was revealed that the early use of PD in combination with inotropic drugs provides the greatest effectiveness of combined therapy and improves the results of surgical treatment.

The effects and consequences of inotropic therapy for heart failure depend on its two main components: the effect on hemodynamic parameters and the calculated doses of their administration, which were observed according to the standards for children of this age group. To date, a large amount of information has been accumulated on the advantages of a combination of catecholamines for the treatment of organ dysfunction in patients with acute heart failure during the correction of CHD using echocardiography data with calculations of cardiac output indicators.

Depending on the duration of combination therapy, a positive effect on hemodynamic parameters was observed in both subgroups (Table 4). The parameters of blood pressure, heart rate, and central venous pressure in patients of group 2a were better compared to group 1a ($p < 0.05$).

It should be suggested that treatment of patients with AKI in group 2a with cardiotropic drugs in combination with PD was more convincing and effective than treatment in group 1a, which was reflected in the parameters of BP, HR, CVP ($p < 0.05$). When analyzing the effect of combination therapy in both subgroups on the treatment results, it was found that patients in group 2a showed an improvement in central hemodynamic parameters to target values - CI, CI, EF ($p < 0.05$). The analysis results showed that therapeutic measures with early use of PD had a significantly higher efficiency in this subgroup ($p < 0.05$). Compliance with the recommended combinations of vasopressors made it possible to significantly increase the effectiveness of the therapy. It should be noted that in addition to the presented parameters of peripheral hemodynamics, the values of OPSS and OLSS were also determined, which significantly differed from group 1a, having decreased by 7.4% and 5.5%, respectively ($p < 0.05$). Positive trends were found in both the LVSI and RVSI values, which improved by 9.1% and 25%, respectively

($p < 0.05$). It should be noted that the qualitative component of vasopressor therapy can have a significant impact on the course of the intraoperative and early postoperative periods in young children undergoing extensive cardiac surgery.

Table 4

Hemodynamic characteristics in the studied patients

Indicators	eGFR ≤ 89 ml/min/1.73 m² (n= 34)		
	Group 1a (n=21) adrenaline + dobutamine + milrinone	Group 2a (n=13) adrenaline + dobutamine + milrinone + peritoneal dialysis	
BP, mmHg	56.2 \pm 4.3	61.2 \pm 3.5	<0.05
HR, mmHg	148 \pm 10	136 \pm 13	
CVP, mmHg	13 \pm 3	10 \pm 3	
CI l/min/m²	1.85 \pm 0,4	2.2 \pm 0.7	
UI, ml/kg/m²	31 \pm 11	34 \pm 11	
LVEF	53 \pm 10	56 \pm 13	
OPSS, (dyn/s/cm³)	1139 \pm 181	1055 \pm 302	
OLSS, d/min/m²	108 \pm 35	102 \pm 30	
LVSI, gm/beat/m²	32.9 \pm 8.2	35.9 \pm 10.6	
RVSI, gm/beat/m²	4.17 \pm 0.51	5.22 \pm 0.51	

Note: APsr – mean arterial pressure, HR – heart rate, CVP – central venous pressure, PAWP – pulmonary artery wedge pressure, CI – cardiac index, SI – stroke index, EF – ejection fraction, TPR – total peripheral vascular resistance, TPVR – total pulmonary vascular resistance, LVSI – left ventricular stroke work index, RVSI – right ventricular stroke work index.

Treatment results. One of the results of this study was the identification of the need to use CysC in calculating eGFR after cardiac surgery in children, indicating high information content in assessing renal dysfunction and as a predictor of an unfavorable prognosis in AKI. The data obtained on the basis of a modern biomarker of renal function - CysC, explains the feasibility of its implementation in the strategy of complex treatment of AKI. Dynamic assessment of the clinical condition, combined cardiotropic and inotropic therapy, maintenance of adequate volemic state and elimination of fluid overload when using PD in the postoperative period in children with CHD who underwent high-tech surgical interventions caused not only a decrease in the incidence of AKI, but also the severity of renal dysfunction and, therefore, led to improved hemodynamic stability. This therapeutic approach is characterized by ease of administration, high efficiency in balancing the hemodynamic profile and stabilizing renal function. In addition, a reliable decrease in urea, creatinine, blood CysC, microalbuminuria, improvement in renal perfusion and an increase in SCF, diuresis rate were revealed.

In conclusion, it should be suggested that the obtained results allow us to recommend in the future continuation of the study of the express test for CysC, to study its effectiveness for assessing eGFR to improve the quality of prognosis of perioperative AKI outcomes.

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